

Survey

The Regions4Climate project brings together 44 partners from 13 different European countries to demonstrate innovations that enhance societal resilience to the impacts of climate change. Based on cross-sectoral strategies created by and for people, the project partners will collaboratively develop and implement novel social, technological, digital, business, governance, and environmental solutions to reinforce adaptive capacity and minimise vulnerability to climate impacts.

As a part of Regions4Climate (WP4), the University of Helsinki and SEI Tallinn are assessing the governance contexts, including the related policy instruments for climate resilience. For these assessments, we are mapping out governance contexts with regards to how climate resilience and adaptation is organized across different levels of governance and across different policy sectors, planned and steered, and who is participating in it. The purpose of this is to analyze the effectiveness of existing governance arrangements for climate resilience and provide recommendations on possible improvements, taking into account regional differences.

We are also mapping out policy and other steering instruments related to equitable climate resilience at regional level. This survey will be used to create a baseline understanding of the different influential instruments in use in each region. This, together with the desk analysis of actual policies form the basis for discussions to be held during stakeholder workshops in Autumn 2024/Spring 2025. These discussions will be organised as a part of Regions4Climate's Just Transitions Roadmapping process (WP2). These discussions will be about the alignment of existing policy and steering instruments for regions' ambitions related to equitable resilience, as well as potential opportunities within this context. These will form the basis recommendations related to policy instruments at the regional level.

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Glossary for terms used in the survey

Authority-controlled means that the instrument is initiated and coordinated by an official public authority/government body, in contrast to e.g., a guiding strategy for regional development that is put forth by a non-governmental organisation. Being a public authority does not require having legislative powers.

Climate resilience is defined as the enhancement “of the capacity of society and the natural systems we rely on to persist, adapt and transform, in anticipation of and response to disruption and crises” (Lager et al., 2023, p. 4). This is in line with the understanding of adaptation from small incremental measures to larger transformative societal changes.

Equity refers to the concept of fairness and justice within a various context. It includes ensuring that all individuals have access to the same opportunities, resources and treatment, accounting for their specific needs and capacities. Some examples of legal frameworks or policies that explicitly support equity could include regulations that require specific standards of participation or engagement of vulnerable groups; accessibility-related regulations for public buildings, or sectoral or cross-sectoral plans that specifically include a focus on vulnerable groups, etc.

Legal frameworks and policies are documents put forward by authorities **or other organisations**, e.g., NGOs or agencies, to steer climate resilience-related action in the region, e.g., permitting, prohibiting, commanding or setting the intentions. See Table 1 for sub-categories. Note: we are intentionally interested in official policy instruments that come from authorities (e.g., legal frameworks, regulations, strategies, plans), but also less formal ones (strategies, plans, roadmaps) that are initiated by other types of active organisations.

Regional development policies support the present and future wellbeing of the societies and usually focus on economic conditions, but also can touch on other topics of importance to the region, and determine its future development. Examples include one or multiple regions’ Development Strategies, Regional Plans for Economic Development, Regional Development Plans/Strategies, Action Plans, Regional Programmes. These development policies are not usually sector specific and do not refer to RIS3 Smart Specialisation Strategies or Innovation Plans.

In this survey, we acknowledge the regional differences in terms of administrative division. Thus, in this survey we use the following terms to define the levels of governance:

- national
- regional (refers to any level below national and above municipal as per the administrative division. This can include autonomous regions, counties and county associations, groups of municipalities)
- local (i.e., municipal)

Region: [Region name]

Respondents: (please add all the names of the people and their organisations (if different) who have contributed to filling in the survey)

Click or tap here to enter text.

Legal frameworks and policies

Through work in the Regions4Climate project, we have established that the following legal frameworks and policies¹ that are relevant for climate resilience² for your region at multiple levels³ (See Table 1).

Q1. Review Table 1 and add any missing instruments, their hyperlink, their levels, and whether they are controlled by a public authority (and highlight in **red** any incorrect instruments). You do not need to fill out more than the **10 main ones** that influence climate resilience in your region. Please, be specific so that we can find more information about these instruments if needed.

¹ See Glossary for definition

² See Glossary for definition

³ These instruments have been collected through the Regions4Climate Grant Agreement, WP2 T2.1, T2.4, WP6 T6.1, as well as the Regions4Climate project Annual Meeting in Sitia 04/2024.

Table 1. Legal Frameworks and policy instruments for climate resilience

Types of legal frameworks and policies <u>guiding climate resilience in your region</u>	Name of legal framework or policy	Hyperlink	Level (N=National, R=Regional, L=Local)	Authority controlled (Yes/No) ⁴
Regulations/legislation (e.g., flood risk regulation, building regulation, climate law)				
Standards or guidelines (e.g., spatial planning, infrastructure performance)				
Planning documents (e.g., Strategic planning, adaptation planning)				
Agreements & Intergovernmental mandates (e.g., mandate to cooperate with other same level (trans-boundary) or different level government in relevant policy area; PPP agreements in relevant policy area)				

⁴ See Glossary for definition

Q2. Is adaptation and climate resilience steered in the region primarily through (choose one from the drop-down menu):

Local (municipal) climate strategies / plans

Q2a: If National Climate Law was selected above, does the law set requirements for the region to adapt / develop a strategy?

Yes No

Q3: Is climate resilience integrated into main policy sectors or is it a stand-alone policy sector?

stand-alone

integrated

mixed (if so, please elaborate): [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Q3a: If integrated / mainstreamed into other policy sectors (e.g., energy sector, coastal protection sector, land use, etc.), at what administrative / governance levels (mark all applicable)?

national

regional

local

Q4: Are the climate resilience objectives aligned/coherent across different levels of governance?

Yes No

If yes, at which levels:

national

regional

local

Q5: Related to the previous question, is there a legal framework that regulates the coherence and alignment of adaptation across levels of governance?

Yes No

Q6. Are tasks assigned and conferred to the appropriate levels to align with the mandates and competencies?

Yes No

Q7: Is there a legal division / assignment of responsibilities to adapt across levels?

Yes No

Q7a: If yes, is it defined at:

- national level
- regional level
- local level

Q8: Are there specialized institutions / organizations that coordinate adaptation and climate resilience or is adaptation coordination added as a function to existing organizations?

- specialized
- added as a function to an existing organization
- no organization is responsible for coordination

Q9. Are there legal frameworks and policies in other sectors (e.g., energy sector, coastal protection sector, land use, etc.) that impact (positively support or negatively impact) climate resilience and adaptation progress or action in your region?

- Yes No

Q9a: If yes, please name the 3 most influential ones each and explain how they positively or negatively impact regional adaptation and resilience?

Legal framework or policy from other sector that has <u>negative</u> influence on adaptation and resilience in region	Description of or reason for negative influence
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Legal framework or policy from other sector that has <u>positively</u> influence/support adaptation and resilience in region	Description of or reason for positive influence/support
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Q9b. Are there legal frameworks or policies (from any other sector) that explicitly support equity⁵ across policy sectors, including adaptation and resilience?

- Yes No

⁵ See Glossary for definition

If yes, which ones? (name up to 3 legal frameworks or policies, their level (N, R, L) and links to more information about them here:

Legal framework or policy	Link	Level (N=National, R=Regional, L=Local)
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Q10. Would you consider the following document the most influential regional development policy⁶ (policy, strategy, plan) and hyperlink for your region?

Yes No

If not, please enter the correct regional development policy and its link on the line below the given policy.

Regional development policy	Hyperlink

Climate resilience funding and financial instruments

Q11. Is there dedicated funding for adaptation?

- This funding is continuous and secured for the whole policy cycle (planning, implementation, monitoring & evaluation, re-planning)
- This funding is available for planning and implementation
- This funding is available for planning only
- This funding is project-based or for limited time only
- There is no dedicated funding
- Other (Please explain):

Click or tap here to enter text.

⁶ See Glossary for definition

Q12. Table 2 is a table of financial instruments relevant for climate resilience for your region. Please fill out Table 2 to add instruments, their hyperlink or further details, and their levels, and whether they are controlled by a public authority. You do not need to fill out more than the **10 main ones** that influence climate resilience in your region. Please be specific so that we can find more information about these instruments if needed.

Table 2. Financial instruments for climate resilience

Type of funding or financial instrument <u>guiding climate resilience in your region</u>	Name of instrument	Hyperlink or further details	Level (I=International, N=National, R=Regional, L=Local)	Authority controlled (Yes/No)⁷
Incentivising (e.g. grants or subsidies, green bonds or loans, insurance, direct expenditure for implementation of policy measures, tax incentives/tax breaks, research funding)				
Penalising (e.g. deterrent taxes, user charges)				
Budget allocation/Direct programming expenditure on goods & services (e.g. for planning and implementation of adaptation/DRR strategies, awareness raising, early warning systems, relocation costs, flood protection, restoration, etc.)				

⁷ See Glossary for definition

Project related funding with co-financing requirements (e.g. LIFE Programme, Interreg, etc.)				
Project related funding with <u>no</u> co-financing requirements (e.g. National level project funding, Horizon Europe)				
New innovative financial instruments (e.g. new business models that the region is involved in establishing, labelling)				
Demonstration projects on publicly controlled land/buildings/facilities/processes paid 100% by sub-national level public funding				
Public procurement (e.g. embedding requirements into contractual agreements related to infrastructure and public services)				
Other				

Q13. Are there financial instruments from other sectors, (e.g., energy sector, coastal protection sector, land use, etc.) that impact (positively support or negatively impact) climate adaptation and resilience in your region?

Yes No

Q14a: If yes, please name the 3 most influential ones and explain how they positively or negatively influence regional adaptation and resilience?

Financial instrument from other sector that has <u>negative</u> influence on adaptation and resilience in region	Description of or reason for negative influence
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Financial instrument from other sector that has <u>positive</u> influence/support adaptation and resilience in region	Description of or reason for positive influence/support
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Informational instruments (Awareness raising & guidance)

Through work in the Regions4Climate project, we have established that the following informational instruments are relevant for climate resilience for your region at multiple levels (See Table 3).

Q15. Review and fill out Table 3 with any missing instruments, their hyperlink or further details, their levels, and whether they are controlled by a public authority (and highlight in **red** any incorrect instruments). You do not need to fill out more than the **15 main ones** influence climate resilience in your region. Please be specific so that we can find more information about these instruments if needed.

Table 3. Informational instruments for climate resilience

Type of informational instruments guiding climate resilience in your region	Name of instrument	Hyperlink or further details	Level (I=International N=National, R=Regional, L=Local)	Authority controlled (Yes/No)⁸
Knowledge mobilisation (Building formal and informal relationships between research producers and users) and knowledge sharing networks (Covenant				

⁸ See Glossary for definition

of Mayors, ICLEI, regional networks supporting resilience)				
Engaging with indigenous and local knowledge on adaptation/resilience				
Knowledge generation (projections, scenario development and assessments used specifically for regional resilience planning e.g. regional risk assessments)				
Monitoring and evaluation				
Public outreach				

Q16. Which of the instruments above provide guidance, coordination and information dissemination at:

Description	Policy instrument from Table 3
across all levels of governance and sectors (national & regional)	Click or tap here to enter text.
at the regional level across sectors	Click or tap here to enter text.
from national to regional only (vertical)	Click or tap here to enter text.
at the national level across sectors & policy domains (horizontal)	Click or tap here to enter text.
Other (Please explain):	Click or tap here to enter text.

Q17. Are there Informational instruments in other sectors, (e.g., energy sector, coastal protection sector, land use, etc.) that positively support or negatively impact climate adaptation and resilience in your region? Yes No

Q17a: If yes, please name the 3 most influential ones and explain how they negatively influence regional adaptation and resilience?

Informational policy instrument from other sector that has <u>negative</u> influence on adaptation and resilience in region	Description of or reason for negative influence
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Informational policy instrument from other sector that has <u>positively</u> influence/support adaptation and resilience in region	Description of or reason for positive influence/support
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Instruments: General

Q19. What are the 10 most influential instruments guiding regional climate resilience? Please refer to any of the instruments listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3. “Most influential” means having the most influence on action in the region/at the regional level.

10 main instruments guiding regional climate resilience (you can write in the name of the instrument in the tables above, e.g. Region X Climate Adaptation Strategy)
Click or tap here to enter text.
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Q20. Are there instruments that are not currently considered influential, but that have in your opinion potential to guiding regional resilience if strengthened? Please refer to any of the instruments listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Instruments with potential	Level (N=national, R=regional, L=local)	Key coordinating actor	Reason for potential
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.
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Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.	Click or tap here to enter text.

Actors

Q21. Which actors are engaged in climate resilience in the region? Please, mark all applicable:

- public sector
- private sector
- third sector (NGOs, non-profit organisations, associations, civil society)
- boundary organizations (bridging science & policy)
- networks (e.g., ICLEI, C40, etc)
- private citizens and households

Q22. Is the private sector required to or incentivized to participate in adaptation?

- Yes No

Q22a. If Yes, the participation of private sector is (check all that apply)

- voluntary
- financially incentivised
- through PPPs
- legally required by a climate/adaptation/resilience framework